

European networks observing the atmospheric boundary layer

Instruments Chapter: Overview

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To observe the Atmospheric Boundary Layer (ABL) on the European scale, PROBE has focused on ground-based profiling instruments which are integrated into European-wide observational networks. The most prominent networks are realized through EUMETNET E-PROFILE and the European research infrastructure ACTRIS. Four types of „network-ready“ ground-based remote sensing profilers are covered: **ceilometers, Doppler lidars, microwave radiometers** and **cloud radars**. Due to the rapid developments of the last years, PROBE has also identified Uncrewed Aerial System (UAS, drones) as profiling systems with a very high potential for future network operation. This is manifested by the 2024 WMO-Demonstration campaign for UAS, a collaborative project to evaluate the potential of weather sensing using UAS in operational upper-air measurement networks.

PROBE Working Groups 3 (Tailored Measurement Networks) and 4 (Operation and Data Quality) have the goal of defining network standards and procedures for successfully operating the above-mentioned ABL profilers in European networks. For this, PROBE has been integrating the E-PROFILE and ACTRIS communities with each other, so that the ABL-profilers can be efficiently operated in any observation network.

In the following, sub-chapters for each ABL-profiling instrument are presented which are intended to give a general overview of the available instruments and their capabilities and then to address the Deliverables that were derived to operate these instruments successfully in networks. The following Deliverables are addressed for each instrument separately in the corresponding instrument chapters

Deliverables Working Group 3

D3.1: Data and format standards for operational dissemination in real time for all products.

D3.2: Report presenting minimum requirements for contributors to participate in networks.

D3.3: Recommendations and prototype tools for centralized processing and network monitoring.

Deliverables Working Group 4

D4.1: Recommendations for configuration, operation, calibration, quality control

D4.2: Delivery of algorithms or codes to produce level1 and level2 data products, handling manufacturer and generation heterogeneity with uniform metadata

D4.3: Report on instrument field tests and investigations

Each sub-chapter is structured in the following way, whereby the Deliverables are specifically covered as given below. Note, that Deliverables 3.2 and 4.3 are covered in the Chapter 2:

Chapter 2a:

JND European networks observing the atmospheric boundary layer: Overview, access and impacts - Chapter 2a: Automatic low-power Lidar and Ceilometer (ALC):

<https://zenodo.org/records/11211873>

Chapter 2b:

JND European networks observing the atmospheric boundary layer: Overview, access and impacts - Chapter 2b: Doppler Cloud Radar (DCR):

<https://zenodo.org/records/11566494>

Chapter 2c:

JND European networks observing the atmospheric boundary layer: Overview, access and impacts - Chapter 2c: Doppler Lidar (DL):

<https://zenodo.org/records/11561263>

Chapter 2d:

JND European networks observing the atmospheric boundary layer: Overview, access and impacts - Chapter 2d: Microwave Radiometer (MWR):

<https://zenodo.org/records/11422901>

Chapter 2e:

JND European networks observing the atmospheric boundary layer: Overview, access and impacts - Chapter 2e: Unmanned Aircraft Systems (UAS):

<https://zenodo.org/records/11448418>

Part1 Instrument overview

1.1 Introduction & basic measurement principles

1.2. Overview of quantities that can be derived

1.3 Tabular overview of instrument types: resolution, range, available products, uncertainties/limitations

Part 2 Recommendations for network operation (D4.1)

2.1 Instrument set-up (site selection criteria, permissions, etc.)

2.2 Maintenance

2.3 Calibration

2.3 Measurement configuration, Link to SOPs

2.4 QA/QC

Part3 Data formats and file standards (D3.1)

3.1 Data formats

3.2 File standards

Part4 Processing algorithms and retrieval codes (D3.3, D4.2)

4.1 Single instrument retrievals

4.2 Data processing chains